

Does Relative Motion Dictate the Existence of NonRelative (Photonic) Velocity?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 8, 2022

Relative motion, which applies to objects with nonzero rest mass, is a common phenomenon. The Lorentz transformation which describes such a transformation, however, utilizes c the speed of light in a vacuum which seems to have nothing to do with a particle with nonzero rest mass. One may consider c a cutoff on the velocity of a particle with rest mass (as is usually done) and also note that the Lorentz transformation also applies to a photon 4-vector (p =momentum, E =energy).

In this note we argue that relative motion seems to dictate the existence of nonrelative (photon-like) motion which has the same value c as seen in any frame (in a vacuum). For a particle with rest mass m_0 associated with rest energy it is possible to postulate that momentum $p=E(v)/v$. Given that v may be positive or negative, one may argue that a quadratic form is the first to bypass this issue. Furthermore a quadratic form is in keeping with the idea of a dot product if one considers a matrix transformation of $(p=0, E=m_0)$ to (p, E) . In such a case, one may create the relationship $E^2 = p^2/b^2 + m_0^2$ ((1)) such that $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/b^2}$ where b is a constant needed to ensure proper units. A point we wish to make is that one begins with one dispersion relationship namely $p=E(v)/v$ and obtains a result ((1)) which contains two dispersion relationships, the second one being $E=pb$ where $b=c$ the speed of light in a vacuum if one sets $m_0=0$. At the onset the idea of $m_0=0$ is not even considered for relative motion. Thus we argue that $b=c$ is not merely a cutoff, but rather that the formalism for relative motion of a particle with rest mass requires a nonrelative velocity c which is the same in all frames (i.e. light speed). This argument may be strengthened if one considers how x and t transform when seen by a constant moving frame (i.e. relative motion). In such a case we argue that one may see explicitly by forming the dot product $-Et+px$ (which we describe in this note) that there is the possibility of wavelike motion $dx/dt = E/p$ i.e. the second dispersion relationship. Thus the formalism for relative motion (for nonzero rest mass) allows for the existence of an object with nonzero rest mass which undergoes nonrelative motion i.e. has the same speed c as viewed from all frames.

Relative Motion

Relative motion is a common phenomenon in everyday life for objects with rest mass. It is generally known as Galilean relativity and does not dictate the existence of nonrelative motion. Special relativity, however, which fully describes 4-vectors as seen from constant moving frames contains c the speed of light in a vacuum. This is usually considered to be a cutoff for the velocity which a particle with nonzero mass may achieve. With such an interpretation, the existence of relative motion does not dictate the existence of nonrelative motion i.e. photon motion. Furthermore, the same Lorentz transformation describes both the transformation of (p, E) for a particle with rest mass and a photon.

In (1) we considered developing the Lorentz transformation for a particle with nonzero rest mass with no consideration of a photon. We argued that one may have a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at

$t=t_0$ and that when seen from a moving frame this should have energy $E(v)$, $p=E(v)/v$ and $x'/t'=v$. Introducing unitary type matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & av \\ av & a \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

we argued that a metric had to be found such that $(x,t) = (0,t_0) + (x,0)$ yielded a dot product:

$$(E,p) \text{ dot product } (x,0) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

This led to the Lorentz invariant dot product $-Et+px$ and $a = \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$.

At this point b has the units of velocity and represents a cutoff value for v . It may be argued that the cutoff b has the same value in all frames. In other words it represents a constant velocity which is nonrelative. This is surprising because one started with the assumption that $p = E(v)/v$. This is a specific dispersion relationship which holds for a particle with a nonzero rest mass and is associated only with relative motion.

To investigate further, one may consider the dot product $-EE + ppbb = m_0 m_0 bbbb$. This follows from the above ideas or may be postulated independently. For example, one may start with the assumption $p=E(v)/v$ which only holds for a nonzero rest mass particle. Given that v may be positive or negative, one must use even powers (2 being the lowest). This is also in keeping with the notion of a dot product. Then one may suggest:

$$EE = ppbb + m_0 m_0 bbbb \quad ((4)) \text{ which leads to } E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$$

What is interesting is that one starts with one dispersion relationship $p=E(v)/v$ and automatically obtains another by setting $m_0=0$ i.e. $E=pb$ where b represents a nonrelative constant velocity i.e. one that has the same value when seen from all constant moving frames. Thus there must exist a particle with nonzero rest mass in nature which has a constant velocity (in a vacuum) as seen in all constant moving frames.

Wavelike Motion

How does one learn more about this nonrelative motion and its associated particle? We suggest that one should examine the dot product $-Et+px$. We argued above that a Lorentz transformation of a particle with nonzero rest mass leads to $x'/t'=v$ from $(0,m_0)$, $(0,t_0)$. This value as shown in (1) leads to $dA=0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv -E dt/dv + p dx/dv$. One may, however, define a different velocity which also keeps $dA=0$ namely:

$$dA=0 = -Edx + p dt \quad ((5))$$

This couples changes in x and t to E and p and represents wave motion as already known in classical physics (e.g. water waves or waves on a string) i.e. $E=pv$. This is the second dispersion relationship found from $EE = ppbb + m_0 m_0 bbbb$, thus $v=b$ and represents a wave. Thus the formalism for a particle with nonzero rest mass automatically leads to the existence of

a constant nonrelative wave motion. The particle with nonzero rest mass does not follow ((5)) so there are two distinct objects described by the same theory, yet both should exist. An interesting idea is that one starts with only the notion of relative motion (nonzero rest mass) and is led to the existence of zero rest mass nonrelative velocity. As argued, this exists because the dot product $EE = ppbb + momobbbb$ has nonzero E, p solutions for $m_0=0$ as well as the solution $E=mc^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p=Ev$ with $b=c$.

Alternatively, one may consider the matrix ((2)). If one considers a vector (p, E) with $p=Ec$ a nonzero rest mass dispersion relationship, the one obtains a new p' and E' , but $p'=E'c$ i.e. the velocity is nonrelative and does not change. When formulating ((2)) only $m_0=0$ at $x=0$ and $t=0$ was considered, but a second solution of an object which always has E and p such that $E=pc$ is also consistent with the transformation.

Particles-AntiParticles

As a curiosity, one may consider particles and antiparticles. These both have rest mass and relative motion, but may combine to create light which has no relative velocity. Similarly a photon which represents nonrelative motion may create a particle antiparticle pair (under proper conditions). Each of these only has relative motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that a treatment of the commonly experienced phenomenon of relative motion for particles with rest mass automatically allows for the solution of an object with a constant nonrelative velocity (i.e. the photon). In other words starting with one dispersion relationship $p=E(v)/v$ leads to an expression $EE = ppbb + momobbbb$ ($b=c$) which allows for two dispersion relationships, the second following from $m_0=0$ which would normally lead to $0=0+0$ for the relative motion only picture. One might argue that b is a cutoff velocity and that the second solution $E=pb$ ($b=c$) does not exist, but the dot product $A=-Et+px$ suggests a wavelike motion with $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ yielding $E=pv$ and it is known that waves exist classically albeit with a medium. This "wave" would not need a medium and would have a nonrelative velocity which is the same in all frames. As argued in (1) light satisfies this condition.

Thus it seems that the notion of relative motion cannot exist without also having the notion of a constant velocity nonrelative motion.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relationship Between Zero and NonZero Rest Mass in Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2022)